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Glossary

DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
KNAW	Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Books Network
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
SIG	Special Interest Group
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
WG	Working Group

Project overview

Academic books are crucial for research communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). Open access (OA) to these books is essential for promoting Open Science in the European Research Area. The EU-funded OAPEN-EU project aims to strengthen the OAPEN Library, which serves as a vital infrastructure for the curation, hosting, dissemination, and preservation of peer-reviewed long-form publications, including scholarly books, such as monographs, edited collections, and book chapters. The project will align with the EU's Open Access policy requirements. By enhancing services tailored to the specific needs of Horizon Europe-funded publications, the project will actively support the open-access mandates established by the European Commission and the European Research Council.

Introduction

This communication plan details the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities OAPEN will initiate to promote the OAPEN-EU project. The aim is to maximise impact using existing organisational communication channels and networks, including leveraging European Commission contacts to be able to access the research community.

This plan is divided into several sections: a table overview summarising the communication activities, channels, target groups, and KPIs; a detailed explanation of each type of activity and the impact on the relevant stakeholder group; a summary of the different communication channels that will be used in the project; and a conclusion.

Overview of communications activities

This table provides an overview of OAPEN’s communications channels, the planned actions and activities to be communicated, the target groups reached for each activity, its Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and how we will measure their success throughout the project.

Channel	Action type	Activity	Target groups	KPI	Measure
OAPEN Website	Communication	Main access to the collection and deposit service	Researchers, publishers	# of visitors on the EU collection webpage at OAPEN	> 50 visitors per month
OAPEN Blog	Dissemination	Awareness raising	Researchers, publishers	# blog posts	3-4
OAPEN Newsletters	Dissemination	Awareness raising	Researchers, publishers	# of mentions in newsletters	> 4 mentions in newsletters
Social media, BlueSky	Dissemination	Awareness raising	Researchers, publishers, libraries	# of posts on BlueSky	> 10 posts
Social media, LinkedIn	Dissemination	Awareness raising	Researchers, publishers, libraries	# of posts on LinkedIn	> 10 posts
Policy Forum for OA Books	Exploitation, communication	Peer engagement	Funders, policymakers	# of presentations at Policy Forum meetings	1-2
OPERAS OA Books SIG	Exploitation, communication	Stakeholder engagement	Publishers, infrastructure providers, libraries	# of presentations at OA Books SIG	1-2

				and WG meetings	
OA Books Network	Communication	Awareness raising and engagement	Researchers, publishers, funders	# of events	1-2

Table 1. Overview of communication activities

Description of communications activities

Each activity from the table has been grouped into a category and the impact on the relevant stakeholders is noted in the descriptions.

Main access to the collection and deposit service

A dedicated webpage for the European Union collection will be made available on the OAPEN website for researchers and publishers to access. We aim to attract fifty visitors per month to the webpage throughout the project’s duration through our communications.

The deposit service for EU-funded authors will be made available and promoted through social media and other communications activities to increase the dissemination of EU-funded content in OAPEN, ultimately increasing the visibility of the research.

Awareness raising

We will raise awareness and disseminate information about the project among our communities, chiefly researchers and publishers, by publishing blogs (3-4), promoting the collection in the OAPEN newsletter (4 times), and utilising OAPEN social media channels (Bluesky and LinkedIn) to post dedicated communications about the project and its progress (at least 10 posts through each channel). Using social media would also help reach libraries as an additional audience and draw more users towards the webpage and deposit service.

Peer engagement

OAPEN is a founding member of [OPERAS](#), the only research infrastructure that addresses open scholarly communication for European Research Infrastructure in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). OAPEN is a member of the Executive Assembly of OPERAS and jointly operates the Dutch National Node ([OPERAS NL](#)) with the [KNAW Humanities cluster](#). As part of the project, OAPEN will liaise with other OPERAS members and National Nodes about engagement.

In addition, OAPEN plays a leading role in the coordination of the Policy Forum for OA Books (in cooperation with Science Europe and cOAlition S). By working with the Policy Forum, OAPEN will be able to engage with other funders and policymakers by presenting updates on the project at meetings (up to two times).

Stakeholder engagement

As part of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, OAPEN leads the OPERAS OA Books Special Interest Group (SIG). It includes three working groups (WG): the Open Access Books Network (OABN), OA Business Models, and OA Infrastructures. The SIG meets several times a year and during these meetings, OAPEN will present updates on the projects to its WG members (up to two times). By doing so, each WG can also disseminate information to their communities of publishers, infrastructure providers, and libraries.

Open Access Books Network (OABN)

Within the OA Books SIG is the Open Access Books Network (OABN), which is jointly facilitated by OAPEN, Open Book Publishers, and SPARC Europe. OABN is a community forum for engaging with open access books. As such, we will mobilise this group to raise awareness and engage with researchers, publishers, and funders by hosting up to two events during the project.

Summary of OAPEN's communications channels

Newsletters

OAPEN has had a dedicated newsletter since 2012. As of October 2025, the number of subscribers has grown to 1,918 and continues to grow weekly. OAPEN sends quarterly newsletters to this list including key updates, information, and activities (including those of partners). In addition, we have a specific publisher newsletter to correspond with all publishers who participate in OAPEN and library supporter newsletter to correspond with all supporting libraries of OAPEN and the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB).

Website and blog

The OAPEN Library website has just undergone a rebrand and alongside this, the page navigation and content was updated. This makes it a more pleasant user experience all-around. In the last year (October 2024 – September 2025), the website saw 11 million views, with 4.2 million of these being first time views (Google Analytics).

There is a spotlight feature on the website, which allows OAPEN to highlight certain pieces of information and news we want to be shared with our community. In addition, OAPEN has a dedicated blog which can be found both through the website and on Hypotheses, where the blog is hosted. We regularly post blogs on all different topics and sometimes feature guest blogs with partners.

Bluesky

OAPEN has had a Bluesky presence since December 2024 (@oapenbooks.bsky.social). As of October 2025, the account has 670 followers. This number grows daily. We

regularly post updates and news, as well as share our partners' news and events. Much of our community moved to Bluesky around the same time and it's a useful way to engage with all different stakeholders.

LinkedIn

OAPEN started a LinkedIn page ([OAPEN Foundation](#)) at the beginning of 2025 as an additional way to engage with our stakeholders. As of October 2025, it has 345 followers. The page sees a lot of interaction with our partners and from others within our community and we've found it a useful page to share big updates and news.

Webinar for EU-funded researchers

Milestone 5 of the project is to deliver a webinar for EU-funded researchers. This will be delivered as part of Work Package 4 by month 12 of the project.

The webinar will follow a similar format to the recent OABN event '[Publishing Open Access Books: Insights from ERC-Funded Authors](#)'. During the preparation of this event, the ERC Executive Agency supported the OABN with finding appropriate authors to partake in a panel discussion. The authors came from different disciplines and had different publishing experiences, united by their ERC funding. The event was recorded, and a short blog post was shared alongside it shortly after the event.

The planned OAPEN-EU event could follow a similar format, with the inclusion of a walkthrough of the deposit form and process, a demonstration of the EU Collection website and a panel of EU-funded OA book authors.

This event will be organised by the OABN but will require additional support via the EU Project Officer in approaching EU-funded authors and in advertising the event to researchers.

As part of the project's peer engagement, the OPERAS National Nodes will be approached to encourage similar events in regional languages. However, the planning and running of these events is outside of the remit of this project.

Measurement of KPIs

During the project, the KPIs and measures will be recorded and performance against the KPIs will be included in the final deliverable of the project: D4.1 Communication Plan Update due in month 24.

Conclusion

This report has given a short description of planned communication events during the project as well as detailing the possible structure of Milestone Five. An update including performance against KPIs will be included in D4.1 Communication Plan Update.